

Online Repository

Towards Effective Collaboration between Software Engineers and Data Scientists developing Machine Learning-Enabled Systems

This online repository contains the transcriptions of the two Focus Group sessions we conducted in our study. It also comprises a codebook with the codes we generated during analysis, the form we used for characterizing the participants, and a template of the board we designed to enable their discussions. In the following, we outline the material.

Content

Filename	Description
Consent_And_Characterization_Form.pdf	Template of the Consent and Characterization Form
Codebook.pdf	Collection of all Codes created during Open Coding
Focus_Group_1_Transcription.pdf	Transcription of the first Focus Group session
Focus_Group_2_Transcription.pdf	Transcription of the second Focus Group session
Focus_Group_Board.pdf	Template of the Board used during the Focus Group sessions